

Modification of the matrix-reinforcement interface for tailoring wear resistance in co-electrodeposited Ni-SiC

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ABSTRACT

Increasing mechanical performance through fabrication advancements is a cornerstone of materials science. In this work, a nanometric protective Ni layer is applied to SiC reinforcement particles to enhance the wear resistance of co-electrodeposited metal matrix composites. The influence of this modification on the matrix-reinforcement interface is studied through electron microscopy and a novel micro-beam bending methodology. Direct micro-mechanical testing reveals a bonding paradox: the protective layer does not increase nominal interfacial strength, but increases wear resistance. The modification transforms the SiC reinforcement from insulators to surface-conductive particles, fundamentally altering the co-deposition mechanism. This leads to immediate particle encapsulation and a more homogeneous distribution of the reinforcement. Ultimately, protective layer suppresses interfacial porosity and ensures a continuous matrix-reinforcement contact resulting in higher wear resistance.

1. Introduction

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been an important research topic due to their superior properties compared to unreinforced alloys [1] with possible applications in automotive, aerospace, energy, and electronics industry. However, considering mechanical properties, one can understand that effect of reinforcement depends on loading conditions. Addition of ceramic reinforcement to metal matrix leads to higher ultimate tensile strength and higher elastic modulus but significantly lower plastic strain in tensile tests [2]. On the other hand, even a small amount of reinforcement provides significantly higher wear resistance compared to pure matrix material [3]. However, if the amount of reinforcement is too high, the wear for such composite may exceed the wear of matrix [4]. Presumably, it may be caused by the high amount of hard ceramic particles present in wear debris. These observations show that interfacial bonding strength in MMCs plays an important role. Increased interfacial strength may help to avoid crack initiation in tensile as well as decrease the amount of reinforcement in debris for wear tests. The question arises how to provide a manufacturing process that will ensure better bonding, hence better mechanical performance?

Literature review shows that usual strategy for improving mechanical properties of co-electrodeposited MMCs is to optimize fabrication

parameters such as current density [5], electrolyte composition, or mode (direct or pulsed current) [6]. However, this approach may change properties of both matrix and matrix-reinforcement interface. Moreover, quantifying interfacial strength can help to understand the influence of manufacturing parameters on the whole composite and interface separately. Extensive research have been done with aim of understanding co-electrodeposition of ceramic particles in metal matrix. Guglielmi [7], Celis [8] and Fransaer [9] proposed models of the process. Experimental studies [10–13] allowed to understand phenomena occurring at the interface. However, it is still unclear how those processes influence mechanical bonding strength between particle and deposited metal coating. Beyond general process models, local chemical phenomena like surface oxidation specifically dictate the final bond quality.

Our earlier work shows that modification of the interface can lead to higher wear resistance. The aim of this modification was to avoid oxidation of SiC surface from Watts bath during co-electrodeposition of composite coating. Such oxidation leads to a thin interphase layer consisting of oxides, but more importantly – also graphite [11]. While graphite is an excellent solid lubricant [14], its uncontrolled formation at the matrix-reinforcement interface is highly detrimental, as it acts as a low-friction barrier that effectively prevents strong mechanical bonding. Hence, we speculate that suppressing the formation of this deleterious

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Fig. 1. Methodology of sample preparation proposed in this paper: a) Scheme of co-electrodeposition b) front view of the sample after co-electrodeposition with indicated stirring direction and EDS and XRD spots for reinforcement concentration shown c) reinforcement pre-treatment: i) as-received SiC powder ii) SiC powder iii) surface-modified Ni/SiC powder iv) cross-section of Ni-SiC composite coating v) cross-section of Ni-Ni/SiC composite coating Schematic representation (not to scale).

graphite interphase via a protective metallic layer may resolve the interfacial weakening. Furthermore, higher interfacial strength would contribute to higher wear resistance. However, abovementioned work lacked a direct evidence of increasing bonding strength with protective layer.

In this paper, we propose a method of matrix-reinforcement interface modification for increasing wear resistance. This modification consists of applying thin metallic layer onto reinforcement particles before co-electrodeposition. Next, composites, with and without this modification, are characterized by means of scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and wear. Special focus is dedicated to matrix-reinforcement interface which is investigated by novel micro-beam bending method as well as Transmission Kikuchi Diffraction (TKD).

The results show that the proposed surface modification improves the wear resistance of the composite; however, this improvement cannot be straightforwardly attributed to enhanced interfacial bonding strength. Instead, it appears to be primarily associated with a less porous interface as well as a more homogeneous dispersion of reinforcement

particles achieved during co-deposition.

2. Experimental

To systematically investigate the influence of interfacial modification on the performance of Ni-SiC composite coatings, an experimental-numerical workflow was employed. This section details the fabrication procedures, including the electroless Ni-coating of the ceramic reinforcement and the subsequent co-electrodeposition of the composite layers. Furthermore, it describes the comprehensive microstructural and mechanical characterization. The techniques range from SEM, Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS), XRD to TKD and micro-beam bending.

Fig. 1 shows the methodology of sample preparation proposed in this paper.

In the conventional fabrication of Ni-SiC composite coatings, SiC particles are incorporated in the as-received state as reinforcement. In the present study, the particle surface was modified by electroless

Table 1

Ni–SiC denotes composites produced by conventional co-electrodeposition using as-received SiC particles. Ni–Ni/SiC denotes composites produced with surface-modified SiC particles, where a thin Ni layer was applied by electroless deposition prior to co-electrodeposition.

Sample	Average SiC particle size [μm]	Surface modification
Ni–SiC 20 μm	20	no
Ni–Ni/SiC 20 μm	20	yes
Ni–SiC 1 μm	1	no
Ni–Ni/SiC 1 μm	1	yes

deposition of a thin Ni layer prior to co-electrodeposition (Fig. 1c). Surface modification means applying thin metallic layer onto ceramic SiC prior to co-electrodeposition to protect SiC from oxidation. This modification was intended to protect the SiC surface from oxidation in the Watts bath while preserving the overall chemical composition of the composite. Subsequently, Ni–SiC composite coatings with unmodified and modified reinforcement were produced by co-electrodeposition. Next, the composite samples were characterized by XRD, nano-indentation, SEM, EDS, and wear tests. Particular attention was devoted to the matrix–reinforcement interface, which was examined by TKD and by a dedicated method for interfacial bonding strength determination.

2.1. Sample preparation

First, 5 g batches of SiC particles with an average size of 20 μm were coated with thin nickel layer by electroless deposition. The process comprised four main steps, each followed by rinsing with deionized (DI) water and centrifugation. In the first step (cleaning), the SiC powder was ultrasonically treated in 50 ml NaOH solution for 20 min. Subsequently, the particles were ultrasonically treated in 50 ml HNO_3 for 20 min to remove surface contaminants and promote uniform metal deposition.

In the second step (sensitization), Sn^{2+} ions were absorbed onto SiC surface by immersing the particles in 50 ml of a solution containing 80 g/L $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 80 g/L HCl under ultrasonic agitation for 20 min.

After rinsing, the third step (activation) was carried out in 50 ml of a solution composed of 0.5 g/L $\text{PdCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 30 ml/L HCl for 20 min in an ultrasonic bath. This treatment acted as a catalytic catalyst for Sn nuclei by incorporating additional Pd atoms, which serve as nucleation sites for subsequent nickel deposition. All of the above steps were performed using reagents at room temperature. In the fourth step, a thin Ni layer was deposited by immersing the activated particles for 5 min in a preheated electroless plating bath (95 °C, pH = 4) containing $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 30 g/L; $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 30 g/L; $\text{DL-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_5$ – 20 g/L; $\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ – 20 g/L; $\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ – <0.1 g. This specific duration was chosen to ensure the formation of a nanometric-thin layer, providing surface conductivity while avoiding any significant alteration of the overall particle volume or the final chemical composition of the composite.

The same procedure was applied to 5 g batches of SiC particles with

Table 2

XRD results for SiC powder.

Material	ICDD	Structure	20 μm SiC		1 μm SiC	
			Phase content [%]	Crystalline size [nm]	Phase content [%]	Crystalline size [nm]
SiC	04–010–5697	hexagonal P63/mmc 186	50.5	8.8	31.5	9.4
SiC	01–089–2230	rhombohedral R3m 160	10.3	8.1	34.3	20.9
SiC	04–002–9070	cubic F-43m 216	37.9	16	33.5	26.2
Ni	04–008–4279	hexagonal P63/mmc	1.4	13.7	0.7	32.5

Next, those particles were used to prepare co-electrodeposited Ni–SiC composite coatings. SEM images of obtained samples are shown in Fig. 2.

an average size of 1 μm . The use of two particle sizes enabled evaluation of whether the protective Ni layer exerts effects beyond interfacial bonding strength. As a result, four types of reinforcement particles were obtained and subsequently used to produce four corresponding Ni–SiC composite coatings by co-electrodeposition (Table 1).

The co-electrodeposition procedure was identical for all sample sets, and the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1a. The only variable was the type of SiC particles added to the Watts bath. The electrolyte composition was: NiSO_4 (300 g/L), NiCl_2 (45 g/L), H_3BO_3 (45 g/L), SLS (0.075 g/L), KCl (6 g/L), and saccharin (2 g/L). The bath pH was adjusted to 4 by addition of NaOH. Deposition was carried out for 120 min at a current density of 1.8 A dm^{-2} under mechanical stirring at 250 rpm. The substrate was a polished copper plate (technical purity) with dimensions of 50 × 30 × 10 mm. After deposition, the coatings were rinsed and mechanically polished using SiC papers with grit sizes from 320 to 5000 to obtain a flat surface and remove loosely attached particles. This way we avoid wear debris with high amount of hard ceramic particles at the initial part of the wear tests. Thus, polishing is crucial to guarantee that the subsequent wear performance results are primarily governed by the material's microstructure.

2.2. Material characterization

Ni–SiC composite coatings were characterized by SEM (Crossbeam 350, Zeiss, Germany) equipped with EDS and EBSD detectors. EDS was used for determination of local SiC concentration in six spots of around 1 mm × 1 mm shown in Fig. 1b To account for the non-uniform reinforcement distribution and ensure statistical reliability, additional EDS measurements were performed specifically for each wear track, with three independent measurements taken per track. This site-specific approach allowed for a direct correlation between local reinforcement concentration and wear depth, effectively mitigating the influence of sample heterogeneity on the results. Phase composition and crystallite size were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using the Empyrean PANalytical diffractometer. Rietveld analysis was performed with the HighScore software [15]. Measurements were conducted in a standard Bragg-Brentano geometry [16] using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$ radiation with a wavelength $\lambda=1.540598 \text{ \AA}$ and an approximate spot size of 1 mm × 2 mm. The full angle range was from 5° to 150°. The same procedure was applied to Ni-coated SiC powders.

The Ni–SiC interface was examined by transmission Kikuchi diffraction (TKD) on focused ion beam (FIB)-prepared lamellae to resolve the local crystal microstructure. Interfacial bonding strength was determined using the micro-beam bending methodology described in detail and compared between Ni–SiC composite with unmodified SiC (Ni–SiC) and Ni-coated SiC (Ni–Ni/SiC).

Fig. 2. a) Top surface of as-received Ni-SiC 20 μm composite b) Top surface of Ni-SiC 20 μm composite after polishing c) revealed after polishing Ni-SiC 20 μm (unprotected reinforcement) d) revealed after polishing Ni-Ni/SiC 20 μm (protected reinforcement) e) cross-section of sample Ni-SiC 20 μm with 20 μm of thickness; f) Cross-section of sample Ni-Ni/SiC 20 μm with 27 μm of thickness; g) Cross-section of sample Ni-SiC 1 μm with 24 μm of thickness; h) cross-section of sample Ni-Ni/SiC 1 μm with 22 μm of thickness.

Fig. 3. EDS results for Si content.

2.3. Mechanical characterization

Co-electrodeposited Ni-SiC composite coatings were mechanically characterized by nanoindentation and wear tests. For nanoindentation, the indenter tip was calibrated on fused silica to ensure accurate determination of hardness and Young's modulus using the Oliver-Pharr method [17]. Measurements were performed under load control with a maximum load of 30 mN and loading/unloading rates of 0.1 mN s⁻¹. Wear behavior was evaluated using, bi-directional ball-on-flat sliding tribometer with load 5.16 N applied with 5 mm Al₂O₃ ball. The tangential displacement amplitude was 1.5 mm, the frequency was 10 Hz, and the test duration was 8 h.

3. Results

The key outcome of this work is improved wear resistance of Ni-SiC composite due to modification of the matrix-reinforcement interface. In this section, the experimental results will be reported that show how modifying reinforcement surface can change the performance of the composite.

First, the presence and structural characteristics of the electroless nickel layer on the modified SiC particles were first verified using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. As shown in Table 2, a minor Ni fraction was detected in the SiC powders for both particle sizes (20 μm and 1 μm), confirming the successful formation of the metallic coating. The SiC particles themselves consist of nanocrystalline hexagonal,

rhombohedral, and cubic polytypes. The detection of a hexagonal Ni phase indicates a high degree of structural conformity between the thin metallic layer and the ceramic substrate.

Fig. 2a. shows the as-deposited coating surface, where loosely attached particles are visible. Because such particles may interfere with subsequent wear measurements, all samples were mechanically polished prior to further analysis. The polished surface (Fig. 2b) reveals only fully embedded reinforcement particles after removal of loosely bound ones. Representative particles are shown at higher magnification in Fig. 2c and d. In both composites, SiC particles with an average size of 20 μm are embedded in the Ni matrix; however, the Ni-SiC interface differs markedly depending on particle surface state. For unmodified, as-received SiC (Ni-SiC), interfacial porosity is observed between the matrix and reinforcement. In contrast, Ni-coated particles (Ni-Ni/SiC) exhibit a continuous and smooth interface along the particle circumference, including concave surface regions.

Representative SEM cross-sections of the composite coatings are presented in Fig. 2e-h. They confirm that SiC particles are homogeneously distributed throughout the coating thickness. For coatings containing 20 μm particles, the as-deposited thickness before polishing was approximately 50 μm ; therefore, typically only single particles are present across the thickness. Successful co-deposition was achieved for both particle sizes (1 and 20 μm), and no decrease in SiC concentration toward the top surface was observed.

The SiC distribution on the coating surface was subsequently quantified by EDS at multiple locations. Each sample was measured at six

Fig. 4. a) XRD results for each sample with 3 spots b) influence of SiC content on Ni grain size in composites.

spots on the top surface, as indicated in Fig. 1b and Fig. 3.

The results of distribution of Si content (directly connected with SiC content) shows that amount of SiC reinforcement is influenced by the geometry of co-electrodeposition process. Also, this influence is stronger for bigger particles as the content varies more from min to max value. It is also apparent that the influence is the strongest for spots closest to sample edge. There is also influence of protective layer as the corresponding samples (Ni-Ni/SiC) have more even distribution for given reinforcement size. Hence, the specific content of SiC should be taken into account for each wear test.

XRD mapping of the SiC phase fraction at three surface locations (Fig. 4) confirms the spatially non-uniform reinforcement distribution and its dependence on location, particle size, and protective layer. SiC contents were quantified by Rietveld refinement. XRD was also used to determine the crystal structure and grain size of the Ni matrix (Fig. 4a),

with the resulting dependence on reinforcement content shown in Fig. 4b Ni grain size increases with decreasing SiC content and is markedly larger in pure Ni than in the composites, while showing no clear dependence on particle size or protective layer. Ni grains are ~2–3 orders of magnitude smaller than the SiC particles.

Absolute SiC contents and their variations are higher when determined by XRD than by EDS. This discrepancy likely arises from the indirect estimation of SiC from Si concentration in EDS, which tends to underestimate the true SiC fraction. Nevertheless, EDS enables site-specific measurements; therefore, the local Si content from EDS is used in the following wear analysis to compare reinforcement levels. The wear results are shown in Fig. 5.

Considering the wear results (Fig. 5a and b), even a small fraction of SiC reinforcement markedly reduces wear compared with pure Ni. However, at sufficiently high reinforcement contents wear tends to

Fig. 5. a) Depth of the wear groove vs. content of Si from EDS for composites with 20 μm SiC b) depth of the wear groove vs. content of Si from EDS for composites with 1 μm SiC c) AFM surface topography of the Ni-SiC (20 μm) composite coating, showing a cavity left after particle pull-out d) wear groove: stylus profilometry map of the entire groove; e) corresponding line profile (profile 1).

increase. The application of a protective Ni layer on the SiC particles further decreases wear, with a more pronounced effect observed for the smaller particle size.

Because the local SiC content varies across the coating surface, EDS measurements were performed on both sides of each wear groove and averaged to reduce uncertainty associated with the non-uniform reinforcement distribution.

Furthermore, wear was quantified using groove depth rather than volume loss due to the uneven surface. Cavities were observed in the as-

received surface topography, as depicted in Fig. 5c.

Similar cavities were also observed after polishing, prior to wear testing. A representative wear groove containing such a cavity is shown in Fig. 5d.

The presence of the cavities both inside and outside the wear groove indicates that they originate from polishing rather than from the wear process. Consequently, the volume associated with such cavities should be excluded from the wear assessment. Instead of the volume loss, wear was quantified using the wear-track depth averaged from five

Fig. 6. a) TKD - transmission EBSD - geometry of the measurement b) EBSD mapping at Ni-SiC interface - sample Ni-Ni/SiC with protective layer c) EBSD mapping at Ni-SiC interface - sample Ni-SiC without protective layer.

measurements.

Following the macroscopic tests, microscale characterization of the matrix–reinforcement interface was performed. TKD was applied to both Ni-SiC and Ni-Ni/SiC interfaces. As illustrated in Fig. 6, thin lamellae were prepared by focused ion beam (FIB) milling so as to include the Ni–SiC interface together with adjacent Ni matrix for crystal orientation mapping. For both material variants, TKD measurements were conducted at intact interface regions exhibiting direct contact between the matrix and reinforcement.

TKD mapping (Fig. 6b and c) indicates that electrodeposited Ni exhibits locally enlarged grains in the vicinity of large SiC particles. These grains reach sizes of several hundred nanometres, whereas the average

Ni grain size in the composite is ~15 nm. This trend is similar for both unmodified and Ni-coated reinforcement. However, as shown in Fig. 6b and c, the presence of the Ni protective layer leads to relatively larger grains at the interface.

These results indicate that the local chemistry at the surface of ceramic particles promotes grain coarsening in the adjacent Ni matrix. However, as was shown in Fig. 4b, the overall effect of ceramic reinforcement is a reduction of the average Ni grain size in the composite. TKD mapping thus reveals a local grain-size increase toward the SiC interface.

Finally, the interfacial bonding strength was determined for both Ni-SiC and Ni-Ni/SiC composites using the method proposed in [18].

Fig. 7. Interfacial bonding strength of the Ni-SiC interface determined by the micro-beam bending-based FEM/CZM method [18], expressed as the maximum nominal stress in cohesive elements.

Shortly, this approach consists of FEM-modelling combined with Cohesive Zone Elements based on experimental micro-beam bending, enabling characterization of the microscale mechanical behaviour of the matrix-reinforcement interface. The resulting interfacial bonding

strengths are shown in Fig. 7. For Ni-SiC it was 1975 ± 567 MPa, for Ni-Ni/SiC 1350 ± 387 MPa. The protective Ni layer does not increase the interfacial bonding strength; if anything, a slight decrease is observed. The relative standard deviation remains similar for both

Fig. 8. Comparison of co-deposition mechanism depending on surface state a) pure SiC in Ni-SiC sample b) SiC coated with thin Ni layer in Ni-Ni/SiC sample. Ni - t1 - layer of Ni electrodeposited before SiC comes in contact with electrode after time t1; Ni - t2 - layer of Ni electrodeposited after SiC comes in contact with electrode after time t2.

Fig. 9. Difference in top surface of as-deposited co-electrodeposited Ni-SiC: a) SiC particles visible and sticking out of Ni coating for unprotected, pure SiC b) SiC particles covered by Ni layer for SiC particles protected with Ni layer; Change in a distribution of SiC with Si atomic content determined by EDS averaged signal over area of black rectangle in composites around wear groove c) Ni-SiC without protective layer d) Ni-Ni/SiC with protective layer.

material variants (approximately 30%).

4. Discussion

Previous work has shown that applying a protective layer to ceramic reinforcement can improve the mechanical performance of co-electrodeposited Ni-SiC composites [1,19].

To better understand the origin of this effect, the present work employs a direct methodology for determining interfacial bonding strength in composites [18]. A key advantage of this approach is its ability to evaluate interfacial mechanical properties in as-prepared coatings while accounting for the non-planar, geometrically complex matrix–reinforcement interface.

In this study, macroscopic wear behaviour is interpreted in relation to microscale interfacial characteristics. Wear tests revealed that the protective layer on ceramic reinforcement increases wear resistance. Interfacial mechanical behaviour was subsequently examined by micro-beam bending. Fracture surfaces were characterized by AFM, and the resulting data were incorporated into an FEM/CZM framework to determine interfacial bonding strength.

Contrary to expectations, the protective layer does not increase the measured bonding strength.

This observation differs from previous reports indicating enhanced interfacial strength with coated reinforcement [20]. The discrepancy may suggest that the present methodology provides a more representative assessment of bonding in as-deposited composites than approaches used in earlier studies [1,20–22].

For better understanding of increased wear resistance due to protective layer, while bonding strength had not been improved, the detailed material characterization was conducted.

XRD analysis of the Ni-coated SiC powder (Table 2) indicates that the deposited Ni exhibits a hexagonal structure. Electroless Ni coatings are typically reported as partially amorphous or nanocrystalline [23]. However, such behaviour is usually observed for thicker coatings. In the present case, the Ni layer thickness is only a few nanometres, which may promote structural conformity with the underlying SiC substrate. This may suggest an epitaxy-like growth of the nanometric Ni layer on the hexagonal SiC substrate. Such structural alignment likely minimizes interfacial energy and promotes the formation of the continuous, void-free interface observed in subsequent SEM imaging. The observed difference in Ni crystallite size of protective layer, i.e. 13.7 nm for the 20 μm SiC and 32.5 nm for the 1 μm SiC reinforcement could be explained by the variation in specific surface area. In the 1 μm powder, the significantly larger total surface area results in a lower density of nucleation sites per unit area for a given Ni content – assuming the same number of nucleation sites as in 20 μm powder. This lower nucleation density would allow individual Ni crystallites to grow more extensively before impingement, leading to the larger grain size observed in the XRD analysis.

SEM observations (Fig. 2c and d) further show that the protective Ni layer produces a higher-quality Ni-SiC interface. When the protective Ni layer is continuous around the SiC particle, it facilitates the growth of electrodeposited Ni coating onto the particle surface. This effect is attributed to the electrical conductivity imparted to the particle surface, enabling immediate metal deposition upon contact with the cathode [24]. As a consequence, a more homogeneous distribution of reinforcement particles is obtained in the composite coating (Fig. 3). These observations indicate a modification of the co-deposition mechanism. A schematic comparison of embedding mechanisms for unmodified and Ni-coated particles is presented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8a illustrates a co-deposition process typical for hydrophobic, non-conductive particles [25], in which the growing nickel layer gradually covers the particle in a layer-by-layer manner until it becomes fully embedded in the Ni matrix. On the other hand, Fig. 8b shows how the conductive layer on SiC surface alters this process. The particle becomes coated with electrodeposited nickel immediately upon contact with

substrate (cathode). This interpretation is supported by the visual light microscope images shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9a shows that unprotected SiC particles (black) at the coating surface remain uncovered by Ni (grey). In contrast, in Fig. 9b only grey Ni is visible with dome-like structures which are protected SiC particles covered with Ni.

This difference in the co-deposition mechanism also affects the distribution of SiC particles (Fig. 3 and Fig. 9c and d). Ni-coated SiC particles are incorporated and retained more efficiently within the growing Ni matrix, which reduces the probability of particle detachment during deposition. Consequently, protected particles are more readily embedded in the Ni coating. Unfortunately, a direct comparison of absolute SiC contents between Ni-SiC and Ni-Ni/SiC coatings is complicated by the lower initial bath loading of particles in the Ni-Ni/SiC case, caused by particle losses during rinsing and centrifugation in the electrodeless pretreatment. Nevertheless, despite the lower bath loading, higher local SiC concentrations were obtained for Ni-Ni/SiC (e.g., 20 μm particles in EDS spots 1–4 in Fig. 3), supporting the conclusion that Ni-coated particles are more easily co-deposited.

The more efficient incorporation is attributed to the reduced Ni growth thickness required to envelop a conductive particle (Fig. 8). Smaller thickness of Ni coating means shorter time to full absorption which decreases chances of particle detachment. Detachment of loosely absorbed particles may occur due to hydrodynamic forces (electrolyte is being stirred) and direct impact (collision) from other particles [26,27]. The shorter embedding time decreases the probability of detachment caused by hydrodynamic forces in the stirred electrolyte or by particle-particle collisions. A rigorous comparison would require identical particle loading in the bath for both systems, accounting also for the mass contribution of the Ni coating.

Another difference between the samples is the influence of local reinforcement concentration on the Ni matrix grain size (Fig. 4b). While 25 nm grain size was achieved for pure Ni, the addition of SiC led to Ni grain sizes ranging from 12 to 15 nm. This is a typical result of particles acting as physical barriers that inhibit grain boundary mobility during electrocrystallization. The improved wear resistance of the composites relative to pure Ni can be attributed to both matrix strengthening (via grain refinement, Hall–Petch effect) and the presence of hard reinforcement (Orowan strengthening) [28]. However, previous studies indicate that electrodeposited Ni enters the Hall–Petch breakdown regime at grain sizes of \sim 12–15 nm [29]. This is consistent with obtained results from nanoindentation, where nanohardness of the Ni matrices of all four composites is in the range of 6–6.5 GPa, and slightly lower for pure Ni sample with at most 6 GPa. As expected, grain refinement was not expected to significantly enhance mechanical properties. Thus, while the reduced grain size contributes to the superior wear resistance of the composites compared with pure Ni, differences in wear behavior among the composites themselves are governed primarily by reinforcement concentration and distribution, as well as matrix–reinforcement interface characteristics [30].

In line with this interpretation, the matrix–reinforcement interface differs between Ni-SiC and Ni-Ni/SiC composites in both interfacial morphology (Fig. 2) as well as crystal structure in vicinity of reinforcement (Fig. 6). Although ceramic particles are generally known to refine the matrix grain size, even without co-deposition [10], the present TKD results reveal locally enlarged Ni grains at the interface. This suggests that local electrochemical conditions near the particle surface differ markedly from the average deposition environment. Such interfacial grain coarsening has not been reported previously; while multi-layer electrodeposition is known to produce thickness variations around particles [31], corresponding local variations in grain size have not been documented. Further investigation of this phenomenon is therefore warranted.

Finally, the relationship between wear resistance and interfacial bonding strength was subsequently examined. Interfacial bonding strength was determined with a FEM model combined with CZM

Table 3

Quantified quality of the interface - average % of the porous interface is the ratio of the length of the porous interface to the total length of the interface (particle circumference).

	Ni-SiC	Ni-Ni/SiC
Average % of porous interface	44%	14%
Standard deviation [%]	11%	12%

elements prepared based on experimental data of micro-beam bending. The averaged results presented in Fig. 7 indicate a slight decrease in bonding strength with the protective Ni layer, while the relative standard deviation remains approximately 30% for both material variants. Additionally, statistical analysis showed that with $p = 0.12$ there is no statistically significant difference. Thus, the protective layer does not enhance interfacial mechanical strength, even though wear resistance increases in the Ni-Ni/SiC composites.

Fig. 10. Wear track surface of the Ni-SiC 20 μm (a-i); Ni-Ni/SiC 20 μm (j-l); Ni-SiC 1 μm (m-o); Ni-Ni/SiC 1 μm (p-s). For each condition SEM image and corresponding EDS map of oxygen (O) and silicon (Si) is provided.

Next, protective layer markedly improves interfacial morphology by reducing porosity and promoting continuous contact at the matrix–particle interface (Fig. 2). The difference in interfacial porosity for Ni-SiC and Ni-Ni/SiC was quantified by determining the ratio of the length of the porous interface to the total length of the interface (particle circumference) for 10 particles. The results shown in Table 3 prove that there is a significant improvement in interface quality due to application of the protective layer.

The continuous interface with slightly lower nominal strength provides superior particle retention than a porous interface with higher local peak strength, as it prevents the early initiation of detachment cracks. This is supported by Fig. 10.

For Ni-SiC 20 μm we observed cracked interface filled with oxidized debris (Fig. 10a, b and c), which can facilitate detachment of the particle (Fig. 10d, e and f), leaving empty pull-out cavities in the wear track. Later such cavities get filled with wear debris (Fig. 10g, j and i) – as no Si is observed in those spots.

For Ni-Ni/SiC 20 μm with intact interface the behaviour is different – there is continuous interface without the accommodation of the wear debris and cracking (Fig. 10j, k and l).

Similar phenomena occurred for 1 μm reinforcement. For Ni-SiC 1 μm filled cavities (no signal from Si) is shown, whereas intact interface in Ni-Ni/SiC 1 μm avoids accumulation of wear debris in the interface.

Cavities without SiC filled with wear debris for samples with unprotected reinforcement prove that adding protective layer improves reinforcement retention. Furthermore, detached particles contribute to the formation of the wear debris enhancing abrasive wear of relatively soft Ni matrix against hard (SiC) third body. Consequently, the improved wear resistance observed for composites with protected reinforcement is associated not only with more homogeneous particle distribution but also with the more continuous, pore-free interface that provides stronger effective particle retention.

The main limitation for the proposed protective layer approach is that we did not achieve higher bonding strength. Other limitation is material system specificity – SiC is proved to oxidize in Watts bath, whereas other ceramics may respond to protective layer differently.

Building on the findings of the present study, future work will focus on finding and exploring a method to increase bonding strength and understanding how bonding strength influences overall mechanical performance of a composite.

5. Conclusions

1. **Successful Surface Modification:** The application of a nanometric Ni protective layer onto SiC reinforcement via electroless deposition was successfully confirmed. XRD analysis revealed a hexagonal Ni structure on the SiC surface, suggesting high structural conformity between the thin metal layer and the ceramic substrate.
2. **Enhanced Wear Performance:** Co-electrodeposited Ni-Ni/SiC composites demonstrated higher wear resistance compared to pure Ni and conventional Ni-SiC composites. This improvement was particularly evident in composites reinforced with 1 μm particles.
3. **Improved quality of the interface:** Contrary to initial expectations, micro-scale mechanical testing using the micro-beam bending method revealed that the protective Ni layer did not increase the nominal interfacial bonding strength. Instead, the enhanced wear resistance is attributed to the elimination of interfacial porosity and the resulting increase in effective contact area, leading to superior mechanical anchoring of the particles.
4. **Modified Embedding Mechanism:** The introduction of surface conductivity to the SiC particles fundamentally altered the co-deposition mechanism. Conductive particles undergo immediate encapsulation by the Ni matrix upon cathode contact, which reduces the probability of particle detachment caused by hydrodynamic forces or collisions during the process.

5. **Microstructural Impact:** While the addition of SiC leads to matrix grain refinement compared to pure Ni, the specific performance gains of the Ni-Ni/SiC are primarily governed by improved particle distribution and interface quality rather than further matrix hardening. Finally, this study successfully demonstrated a pre-treatment method for increasing mechanical performance of metal matrix composite. The importance of the matrix-reinforcement interface was highlighted.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT by OpenAI in order to correct the spelling and English grammar. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Piotr Jencyk: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dariusz M. Jarzabek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Elżbieta Gadalińska:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Jarzabek DM. The impact of weak interfacial bonding strength on mechanical properties of metal matrix – ceramic reinforced composites. *Compos Struct* 2018; 201:352–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.06.071>.
- [2] Lai L, Wu Y, Yang Y, Wang H, Yang Z, Ding G. Microfabrication and characterization of high tensile strength SiC whisker-reinforced nickel composite coatings by electrodeposition. *J Electrochem Soc* 2019;166(14):D726–36. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0781914jes>.
- [3] Jencyk P, Grzywacz H, Milczarek M, Jarzabek DM. Mechanical and tribological properties of Co-electrodeposited particulate-reinforced metal matrix composites: a critical review with interfacial aspects. *Materials Jun.* 2021;14(12):3181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14123181>.
- [4] Shrestha NK, Masuko M, Saji T. Composite plating of Ni/SiC using azo-cationic surfactants and wear resistance of coatings. *Wear* 2003;254(5–6):555–64. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1648\(03\)00138-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1648(03)00138-8).
- [5] Gül H, Kılıç F, Aslan S, Alp A, Akbulut H. Characteristics of electro-co-deposited Ni–Al₂O₃ nano-particle reinforced metal matrix composite (MMC) coatings. *Wear* 2009;267(5–8):976–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2008.12.022>.
- [6] Mahidashti Z, Aliofkhaei M, Lotfi N. Review of nickel-based electrodeposited tribo-coatings. *Trans Indian Inst Met* 2018;71(2):257–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12666-017-1175-x>.
- [7] Guglielmi N. Kinetics of the deposition of inert particles from electrolytic baths. *J Electrochem Soc* 1972;119(8):1009. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2404383>.

- [8] Celis JP, Roos JR, Buelens C. A mathematical model for the electrolytic codeposition of particles with a metallic matrix. *J Electrochem Soc* 1987;134(6):1402–8. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2100680>.
- [9] Fransaer J. Analysis of the electrolytic codeposition of Non-Brownian particles with metals. *J Electrochem Soc* 1992;139(2):413–25. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2069233>.
- [10] Socha RP, Nowak P, Laajalehto K, Väyrynen J. Particle-electrode surface interaction during nickel electrodeposition from suspensions containing SiC and SiO₂ particles. *Colloids Surf Physicochem Eng Asp* 2004;235(1–3):45–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2004.01.011>.
- [11] Socha RP, Laajalehto K, Nowak P. Oxidation of the silicon carbide surface in Watts' plating bath. *Surf Interface Anal* 2002;34(1):413–7. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sia.1329>.
- [12] Nowak P, Socha RP, Laajalehto K. Influence of the surface properties of silicon carbide on the process of SiC particles codeposition with nickel. *Colloids Surf Physicochem Eng Asp* 2002;208(1–3):267–75. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-7757\(02\)00153-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-7757(02)00153-X).
- [13] Nowak P, Socha RP, Kaisheva M, Fransaer J, Celis JP, Stoinov Z. Electrochemical investigation of the codeposition of SiC and SiO₂ particles with nickel. *J Appl Electrochem* 2000;30(4):429–37. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1003979117146>.
- [14] Huai W, Zhang C, Wen S. Graphite-based solid lubricant for high-temperature lubrication. *Friction* 2021;9(6):1660–72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40544-020-0456-2>.
- [15] McCusker LB, Von Dreele RB, Cox DE, Louër D, Scardi P. Rietveld refinement guidelines. *J Appl Crystallogr* 1999;32(1):36–50. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889898009856>.
- [16] B.D. Cullity, *Elements of X-Ray diffraction*. Addison-Wesley.
- [17] Oliver WC, Pharr GM. An improved technique for determining hardness and elastic modulus using load and displacement sensing indentation experiments. *J Mater Res* 1992;7(6):1564–83. <https://doi.org/10.1557/JMR.1992.1564>.
- [18] Jencyk P, Jarzabek DM, Jurczak G, Nosewicz S. Experimental–numerical characterization of metal–ceramic interfacial bonding via micro-bending. *Int J Mech Sci* 2026;311:111167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmeecsci.2026.111167>.
- [19] Jencyk P, Gawrońska M, Dera W, Chrzanoska-Giżyńska J, Denis P, Jarzabek DM. Application of SiC particles coated with a protective Ni layer for production of Ni/SiC co-electrodeposited composite coatings with enhanced tribological properties. *Ceram Int* 2019;45(17):23540–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2019.08.063>.
- [20] Jarzabek DM, Dziekoński C, Dera W, Chrzanoska J, Wojciechowski T. Influence of Cu coating of SiC particles on mechanical properties of Ni/SiC co-electrodeposited composites. *Ceram Int* 2018;44(17):21750–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.08.271>.
- [21] Guo X, et al. Interfacial strength and deformation mechanism of SiC–Al composite micro-pillars. *Scr Mater* 2016;114:56–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2015.11.018>.
- [22] Jarzabek DM, Chmielewski M, Wojciechowski T. The measurement of the adhesion force between ceramic particles and metal matrix in ceramic reinforced-metal matrix composites. *Compos Appl Sci Manuf* 2015;76:124–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.05.025>.
- [23] Dervos CT, Vassiliou P, Novacovich J, Kollia C. Vacuum heated electroless nickel plated contacts. *IEEE Trans Compon Packag Technol* 2004;27(1):131–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCAPT.2004.825775>.
- [24] Stappers L, Fransaer J. AFM study of the incorporation of particles during electrodeposition. *J Electrochem Soc* 2007;154(11):D598. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2775165>.
- [25] Dedeloudis C, Fransaer J. AFM study of the behavior of polystyrene and glass particles during the electrodeposition of copper. *Langmuir* 2004;20(25):11030–8. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la0362066>.
- [26] Vereecken PM, Shao I, Searson PC. Particle codeposition in nanocomposite films. *J Electrochem Soc* 2000;147(7):2572. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1393570>.
- [27] Berçot P, Peña-Muñoz E, Pagetti J. Electrolytic composite Ni–PTFE coatings: an adaptation of Guglielmi's model for the phenomena of incorporation. *Surf Coat Technol* 2002;157(2–3):282–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972\(02\)00180-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972(02)00180-9).
- [28] Pinate S, Ghassemali E, Zanella C. Strengthening mechanisms and wear behavior of electrodeposited Ni–SiC nanocomposite coatings. *J Mater Sci* 2022;57(35):16632–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-022-07655-1>.
- [29] Schuh CA, Nieh TG, Yamasaki T. Hall–Petch breakdown manifested in abrasive wear resistance of nanocrystalline nickel. *Scr Mater* 2002;46(10):735–40. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6462\(02\)00062-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6462(02)00062-3).
- [30] Rao H, Li W, Luo Z, Liu H, Zhu L, Chen H. Nucleation and growth mechanism of Ni/SiC composite coatings electrodeposited with micro- and nano-SiC particles. *J Mater Res Technol* 2024;30:3079–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2024.04.008>.
- [31] Stappers L, Fransaer J. Growth of metal around particles during electrodeposition. *J Electrochem Soc* 2006;153(7):C472. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2198090>.